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Abstract	This deliverable describes the sustainability strategy for the main outputs of the ACTION project.
Keywords	Sustainability, accelerator, ACTION toolkit, ACTION open data portal.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ACTION project delivered methodologies, tools, guidelines, and methods to support citizen science (CS) projects in becoming more participatory, inclusive and impactful. To do so, ACTION carried out two open calls, selected ten pilots in addition to those already in the consortium from the beginning of the project, set up a citizen science accelerator programme and co-designed the ACTION CS toolkit.

ACTION followed a sustainability-by-design approach, governed by three key principles: openness, co-design and reflexivity. The combination of these principle assure that the project outputs are aligned with users' needs and expectation and facilitate their take up.

Beside this, a sustainability plan has been developed for each of the main project outputs:

- The ACTION citizen science toolkit;
- The ACTION open data portal;
- The ACTION open call approach;
- The ACTION Accelerator;
- The ACTION impact assessment framework and
- The ACTION policy recommendations.

In brief, the ACTION citizen science toolkit will be kept updated for the next four years and will remain available not only on the ACTION website (that will be maintained for the same period), but also on Zenodo and on the EU.Citizen-science portal. The latter, developed by the homonymous support action project, is now managed by the European Citizen Science Association that assures its long terms availability and high visibility. New contents will be also added thanks to the work that will be conducted in the recently awarded project, called Impetus. This project, that see the presence of UKC and T6 can be understood as the continuation and scaling up of ACTION as it will manage open calls and an European prize for CS projects supporting more than 120 projects in the next four years.

The ACTION open data portal is the open science repository of all ACTION outputs (datasets, deliverables, papers, etc.). It is built on top of Zenodo, which has been developed under the European OpenAIRE programme and is operated by CERN. It is meant as a tool to archive and preserve scientific results in all forms long-term. Every time that a resource is uploaded into the ACTION community on Zenodo, it automatically appears in the ACTION open data portal too and this will continue after the end of the project lifetime.

The ACTION open call approach and the ACTION acceleration program should be considered the exploitation of previous EU projects as they are the adaptation and improvement of previous successful experiences. At the same time, they have been included in other proposals and projects such as MediaFutures (www.mediafutures.eu) and Impetus.

The ACTION impact assessment framework will be supported following a Freemium approach, with training and support services provided for free to interested actors and consultancy services offered on a marked base in case more tailored or time-consuming needs should emerge. It will also be included, and adapted as needed, for the upcoming project Impetus mentioned in the previous paragraph. The ACTION policy recommendations

will be available to the community through the ACTION website, its toolkit and on Zenodo. Support materials will also remain available through SlideShare and YouTube.

Besides the above mentioned outputs it is important to mention that all the research outputs, the datasets developed by the ACTION pilots and the articles published in open access journals are all available through the [ACTION community on Zenodo](#) so that they will remain accessible to all interested persons for the future.

1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of the ACTION project was to deliver methodologies, tools, guidance documents and methods to fundamentally transform the way citizen science (CS) is understood and practiced today, to make it more participatory, inclusive, and impactful. To achieve this goal, ACTION:

- Carried out two open calls and selected 10 pilots with interesting, impactful ideas that addressed pollution challenges.
- Set up a citizen science accelerator to support the selected pilots.
- Co-designed the [ACTION citizen science toolkit](#) that includes methodologies, tools and guidelines to guide CS actors in all the stages of a participatory CS project.
- Created the ACTION open data repository to help citizen scientists easily share and publish their research outputs, following the FAIR principles.
- Co-designed an impact assessment framework that considers the value and the transformations generated by CS projects in social, economic, scientific, political and environmental terms.
- Developed a set of policy recommendations at national and EU level.

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the sustainability paths of the above-mentioned outputs now that the project is coming at its end.

2 THE MAIN OUTPUTS OF THE ACTION PROJECT AND THEIR SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGY

ACTION followed *open science principles* and promoted open data, open knowledge, open tech and open access for all to its outputs. These principles are reflected in the sustainability paths described in the next sections and help making ACTION outputs sustainable beyond the end of its funding period. Indeed, an open approach to the sharing of data, information, and knowledge between disciplines, communities, sectors, and society makes the project results available for all to re-use, adapt and build on top of them.

All research outputs, including project deliverables, articles published in open access journals and datasets developed by the ACTION pilots are and will be always available on

Zenodo, on which [a dedicated community](#) was created at the beginning of the ACTION project to facilitate the findability of the project outputs.

Another approach that supports the sustainability of the ACTION outputs is *co-design*. All the project outputs are co-designed and, in some cases, co-developed by engaging the direct users (CS project managers, other EU projects working on CS, researchers, policy workers). This assures that the project outputs are answering the specific needs of the community and make them more usable and easier to adopt and include in the everyday process of the relevant organisations. Besides this, project outputs have been widely disseminated, so that project stakeholders are aware of them (see D.7.3).

Finally, *reflexivity* was another important guiding principle in ACTION and all the activities have been monitored to improve the related outputs; we followed an iterative approach throughout the main technical work packages, which means that core project outputs (such as the components of the ACTION toolkit) have been released in multiple versions to allow us to draw upon stakeholder feedback and ongoing research insights.

In summary, ACTION followed a *sustainability-by-design* approach, governed by three key principles: openness, co-design, and reflexivity. In the following, we explain how these apply to individual project outputs.

2.1 ACTION citizen science toolkit

The ACTION citizen science toolkit includes methodologies, methods, tools, guidelines and other resources that respond to a wide range of citizen science characteristics: online and offline activities, various and evolving goals and scopes, as well as different stages of development: from early ideas to initiatives that have resulted in scientific publications and other forms of impacts.

In the toolkit, CS projects' actors find a variety of resources for task design, quality assurance and validation, community engagement, incentives, and impact assessment, addressing the challenges around the projects' diversity and evolution.

The toolkit covers all steps of the participatory science lifecycle (see Figure 1 below) and offer CS projects tools and know-how to become more open, participatory and inclusive. The participatory science lifecycle is a visual representation, developed by the ACTION consortium, for visualising the main steps a CS project could follow in its development and acknowledges the diversity in disciplines and in involved actors that could characterise CS projects.

Some tools are developed directly by ACTION, while others are a curated selection of complementary tools from outside the consortium.

Figure 1: Participatory science lifecycle

The toolkit:

- is available through the project website. The website will remain online four years after the end of the project hosted and maintained by UPM. The toolkit page will be updated for the same period by KCL.
- A selection of tools and resources developed directly by ACTION will be listed in the EU.citizen-science portal that from January 2022 is maintained by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) providing a good guarantee for long-term availability of such tools and a broader audience. Each tool will be presented separately, but all will be linked to the ACTION project profile so that users will benefit of two different ways of navigating them (separately or as a collection). It is important to consider that EU.citizen-science is not a storage platform so that all the resources available there are actually stored online on other platforms, in the case of ACTION tools, as said, they will be available on Zenodo in the first place.
- The final version of the toolkit will be available as a .pdf file on the ACTION project website. It will be also available through the EU.citizen-science platform.

Moreover, the ACTION toolkit served already as a base for new projects, as it inspired at least two proposals developed by KCL and IGB respectively. One of them: Impetus, will start in the next months and will support the continuous update and enrichment of the toolkit.

Sustainability plan	
<i>Openness</i>	Tools are openly available and accessible in various formats (see above).
<i>Co-design</i>	Tools and resources have been co-selected and co-designed with the ACTION consortium, pilots, and external users, through dedicated face to face and online workshops. ACTION pilots have been interviewed to validate the participatory science lifecycle in practice and generate additional case studies. Moreover, a dedicated social media campaign has been carried out to gather feedback and request additional resources.
<i>Reflexivity</i>	The toolkit was developed continuously through the project lifetime. The first version was published at the end of 2020, and updated with additional content and improvements until the end of the project.

2.2 ACTION open data portal

The [ACTION open data portal](#) is the open science repository of all ACTION outputs (datasets, deliverables, papers, etc.). The repository is built to be self-sustainable beyond the end of the funding:

- It built on top of Zenodo, a well-known catch-all repository for researching that gives service to the open science community. Zenodo has been developed under the European [OpenAIRE](#) programme and is operated by [CERN](#). It is meant as a tool to archive and preserve scientific results in all forms long-term.
- Every time that a resource is uploaded into the ACTION community on Zenodo, it automatically appears in the ACTION open data portal too and this will continue after the end of the project lifetime.
- In addition, Zenodo offers unlimited storage capacity, which is an attractive proposition regarding hosting costs.
- The open data portal uses the same metadata structure as Zenodo, which fosters technical interoperability and reuse.
- The Open Data Portal is able to visualize Research Objects based on the RO-Crate specification.

The ACTION open data portal has been used by ACTION pilots and partners, but can be used also by other CS projects. To this end, UPM created guidelines on how and why to do an open data portal like the action one when running one or more CS project. These guidelines are available in deliverable 4.5 and in the ACTION toolkit.

Sustainability plan	
<i>Openness</i>	All the source code has open licenses and can be used and modified freely.
<i>Co-design</i>	The Open Data Portal was designed taking into account the suggestions of the ACTION consortium and the pilots.
<i>Reflexivity</i>	The portal was developed in two versions, the second one incorporating the feedback received by project partners and ACTION pilots. Additional feedback can be reported using the GitHub platform in the following repository: https://github.com/actionprojecteu/ODP_frontend

2.3 ACTION open call and acceleration programme

ACTION developed a six-month accelerator program to support CS pilots recruited through competitive calls. The accelerator welcomed its first cohort in early 2020, and its second cohort in 2021. The Accelerator model provides pilots with resources and training, tailored to the needs of each citizen science project, including:

- Intensive training at the start of the accelerator on: project design, citizen engagement, data management and preservation, diversity and inclusion, sustainability and impact assessment;
- Mentoring (online) during the pilot implementation phase;
- Tools and infrastructure to host projects and their data according to state of the art IT practices;
- Tools and methods to facilitate participatory data collection and analysis;
- Bespoke consultancy on a diverse set of citizen science challenges, including: data quality, data preservation, GDPR, research ethics, motivating participation, citizen empowerment, EDI (equity, diversity, inclusion), public engagement, and impact;
- Promotion via news on the ACTION web site and on social media, as well as presentation opportunities at the ACTION conference and other related events;
- Peer learning and networking, facilitated through workshops and online tools;
- Webinars on relevant topics, such as data processing, online engagement, or diversity.

During this period pilots got support through a mentoring programme, with one-to-one exchanges, and regular meetings and webinars. The ACTION team worked with the projects to address the most pressing challenges of Citizen Science today such as data quality, open data management, inclusiveness and diversity, impact assessment, economic and community sustainability, etc.

The Accelerator has produced a series of resources, which are integrated into the ACTION toolkit to allow future initiatives to use. This includes:

- An open data platform, and webinar explaining its use
- A data management tool, and a webinar explaining its use

- Webinars on online community building, impact assessment, sociocracy, and other topics as suggested by the pilots
- Guidelines for community engagement, incentives, and sustainability
- Coney conversational survey tool

All webinars are available at <https://actionproject.eu/resources/webinars/>

A series of deliverables document our experience of engaging with our pilot projects and put it in context. The experiences of the ACTION Open Call and Accelerator is documented in the following deliverables:

D2.12 Final Report First Round of the Call (M21 – October 2020) and D2.13 Final Report Second Round of the Call (M33 – October 2021)

These deliverables detail the structure of the Accelerator and the details of delivery, providing sufficient information for others to adapt and implement their own Acceleration programme.

D2.14 Workshop report 1 (M18 - July 2020). The document includes the co-design and rapid prototyping workshops with the 5 resident pilots (carried out before M6) and those with the applications selected from the 1st Open Call.

D2.15 Workshop report 2 (M36 - January 2022). The report focused on the workshops and prototypes co-created with the pilots that joined the accelerator after the 2nd Open Call.

D2.16 White paper of science innovation through citizen science (M36 - January 2022). This report compiles the lessons learned during the operation of the accelerator in a white paper.

D3.3 Summary of round 1 (M18 - July 2020). This deliverable reports on the 1st Open Call in regard to relationships with applicants, the review, selection and negotiation process, call statistics and analysis and learnings for the 2nd Open Call.

D3.4 Summary of round 2 (M30 - July 2021). This deliverable reports on the 2nd Open Call, following the same format as D3.3. In addition, it includes a final call dashboard with the collection and use of call-related data, which alongside expertise and feedback from the reviewers and the Advisory Board. The dashboard has a public and a private part, to allow for exploratory data analysis.

D2.16 White paper on Science Innovation through Citizen Science, which describes potential for innovation in science deriving from alternative modes of research design, organisation and transdisciplinarity emerging in citizen science projects. Sharing examples from ACTION Pilots, it will be made available via the ACTION website and in the ACTION Zenodo Community and disseminated through social media channels.

The ACTION open call and acceleration approach is the result of an array of research and innovation efforts led by the coordinator and their team (first at Southampton, now King's College London), which have facilitated knowledge transfer and helped develop community-driven resources and toolkits for everyone to use. The format draws upon frameworks and practice from open innovation, start-ups and entrepreneurship and has been initially developed in the [DataPitch](#) and [ODINE](#) H2020 data incubators, led by ACTION

coordinator Elena Simperl). It has been adapted and augmented to respond to the realities of CS work, which shares some similarities with start-ups (e.g. lean processes, limited resources), but also differs from them in important ways (e.g. different ways to understand impact, greater focus on grassroots and volunteer contributions).

The work carried in ACTION and in previous projects provided insights on the viability of the format, which is rapidly becoming a point of reference in other contexts. For instance:

- KCL and T6 recently for approved the project IMPETUS, that builds on the ACTION open call and acceleration program and propose its upscaling to larger numbers addressing new and ongoing CS projects;
- Several projects within the SwafS community, including CoAct and EU.Citizen-Science, asked to learn more about the ACTION Open call: several group and one-to-one meetings have been organised to this end and the ACTION open call documentation has been made available to other consortia that adapted it to their specific needs.
- KCL and experts from T6 are part of another H2020 project, called [MediaFutures](#) which has been designed building on from the ACTION experience and that brings together start-ups, artists and citizens to fight challenges around online disinformation and disengagement;
- UPM, KCL, Cefriel and experts from T6 submitted a proposal (greenACTION) under the GreenDeal call for proposal in 2021 designing a program based on the ACTION one with the addition of other crowdfunding mechanisms. Unfortunately, the proposal was not financed but will probably be re-submitted if new opportunity will emerge.
- A proposal “Post-Extractive Landscapes” was submitted by Kat Austen (Studio Austen) to the PEEK (Programme for Arts-based Research) from the Austrian Science Fund, for participatory artistic research into the mining landscape of the Jiu Valley in Romania, which proposes the use of both the diversity and inclusion guidelines and impact assessment methods developed during ACTION. This is currently under evaluation.

Another important output of the accelerator is the *community of CS projects* working on pollution-related themes and it is our aim to make the community self-sustainable after the end of ACTION. To do so we created a mailing list that supports constant exchange not only between the CS projects and the ACTION consortium but also among the CS projects. The mailing list was moderated so to foster autonomous networking among the projects and will be transferred to the EU-Citizen-Science mailing list at the end of the project.

Finally, the CS projects working on light pollution have been invited and accepted to join the Star4All foundation as a community able to support them in further exchanges on this topic and as an umbrella organisation towards which the project could access additional funds and reach wider visibility.

Sustainability plan - accelerator, including open call	
<i>Openness</i>	The open call process and evaluation process are described in detail in the open call documents (guide of applicants, etc.) available on the ACTION website. The deliverables describing the acceleration program and its achievements are available on the project website and on the ACTION community on Zenodo. Lessons learned from the acceleration program have been elaborated in the white paper and are also available through the ACTION website and the ACTION community on Zenodo.
<i>Co-design</i>	The open call process and the acceleration program were based on previous successful projects and adapted to ACTION thanks to the feedback of ACTION partners, especially its resident pilots. It has been further improved with the feedback of the first cohort pilots. The Accelerator programme was designed in response to the pilots' needs. Initially, this was done according to value elicitation, self-identification of needs and analysis of the projects plans. This was further iterated on through continual feedback during both accelerator rounds, and consolidated feedback from mentors and projects at the end of Round One.
<i>Reflexivity</i>	After the end of the first open call the whole process was discussed before planning the second open call for taking on board the lesson learned. The first accelerator kick-off workshop was evaluated by participants and lessons learned have been used for the planning of its second edition.

2.4 ACTION impact assessment framework

The ACTION impact assessment framework has been co-designed with the help of ACTION partners, especially the resident pilots in the first part of the project. It has then been applied to 16 projects and improved constantly throughout the lifetime of the project thanks to their feedback and related lesson learned.

The ACTION impact assessment framework is a modular, quali-quantitative methodology supporting CS projects to describe and quantify, when possible and advisable, their positive impacts. It considers scientific, social, economic, political and environmental impacts and it

also helps projects in analysing their transformative potential: i.e. their capability to change the state-of-art, the work-as-usual in a specific sector or field (such as research, for example).

Each of the above-mentioned areas of impact are articulated in several sub-dimensions including but not limited to: impact on community empowerment, inclusiveness, civic and political participation, impact on learning and impact on behavioural change.

The methodology is fully operationalized so that each dimension is “translated” in indicators and variables and accompanied by questionnaires that have been tested within ACTION and that are now available in different languages.

While the impact assessment process, data gathering and analysis for the ACTION 16 projects has been supported by the ACTION team, accompanying materials and a video tutorial have been developed so that future CS projects will be able to use the framework in an autonomous way. Its modularity and flexibility, indeed, allow new CS projects to design their own impact assessment path, using and adapting that of ACTION to their specific needs. All the above is included in the [ACTION toolkit](#) and is also available in D5.10. All the questionnaires and other support materials, including the webinar, are also available on Zenodo.

The ACTION impact assessment methodology attracted the attention of several CS projects within and outside the SwafS community. The methodology has been presented in at least six conferences; it is described (in a summarized way) in a published article (Grossberndt et al, 2021) and is going to be published in a book dedicated to impact assessment for CS projects to be published in 2022¹. At least 10 one-to-one meetings with CS projects outside ACTION have been organised to provide them with support for the use of the ACTION impact assessment framework. This support work will continue also after the end of the ACTION project.

Indeed, T6 and DRIFT will invest their own resources beyond the end of funding period to offer support in the long run (for at least 2 years). A double licensing model will be followed, it consists of the following levels of service:

- free support if the assistance needed is related to the already available resources and limited to basic training and information provision;
- premium, if the request for support implies more demanding work, such as adaptation of the framework, actual application of it in terms of a specific project (data gathering and analysis) or more in depth, long training.

T6 and DRIFT, indeed, already have business and pricing models for this kind of service provision.

Finally, the ACTION impact assessment methodology and the related experience will be further exploited by T6 in future proposals (and it has been already included in at least 5 proposals recently submitted one of which successful: Impetus). Indeed, one of the main services offered by T6 Ecosystem is impact assessment of participative research and innovation process and the experience conducted in ACTION improved considerably the company's capacity to offer this service to the CS and alike communities.

¹ The book will be a special issue of the journal of the Austrian Platform for research and technology policy. Evaluation (<https://www.fteval.at/content/home/journal/aktuelles/index.jsp?langId=2>)

Sustainability plan - impact framework and use	
<i>Openness</i>	<p>The deliverable describing the ACTION methodological framework (D7.1) and the data gathering tools developed during the project (D7.2) are available in Zenodo, in the ACTION open knowledge space and are included in the ACTION toolkit.</p> <p>A video tutorial, a power point presentation and other support materials accompany the framework in order to make it more accessible and easier to use. The use of the impact assessment framework after the end of the project will have a free and premium resourcing model.</p>
<i>Co-design</i>	<p>The impact assessment framework has been co-designed in its first version with the ACTION partners during a dedicated meeting; then ACTION pilots provided feedback for its further improvements that are reflected in its final version and in the ACTION toolkit.</p>
<i>Reflexivity</i>	<p>The impact assessment framework is modular and flexible. It has been personalised to each of the ACTION pilots and each application provided important input to its further improvement. The final version of the methodology emerged thanks to this process. The questionnaires and other data gathering tools have been developed following an iterative process and are now included in their final version in the ACTION toolkit</p>

2.5 ACTION policy recommendations

The ACTION policy recommendations are recommendations for policymakers, policy workers, citizen science actors, and scientists to support this mainstreaming process of citizen science. This implies for citizen science to live up to its potential to support administrations to formulate policies for our grand societal challenges, through bridging policy with society and science.

The recommendations have been developed through the engagement with actors from the broader citizen science ecosystem across five European countries: Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Spain, and the United Kingdom. Based on a context scoping per country, that included desk research, interviews and possibly a focus group we co-designed a masterclass in each country with relevant local stakeholders from the citizen science and policy ecosystem, tailored to local needs and challenges. The five masterclasses also aimed to form or strengthen the local network by providing extensive information on the participants and the opportunity to network, to avoid being isolated events. In total, 111 participants joined, which whom we have co-created recommendations to mainstream citizen science in their countries.

After each country masterclass we asked participants to specify strategies to mainstream citizen science in their country in a questionnaire, which 47 participants filled in. We suggested 3-5 strategies based on the scoping analysis and masterclass discussions, but also gave participants the option to suggest strategies and comments. Based on all these inputs we formulated a final set of recommendations to mainstream citizen per country. Each masterclass is briefly described in a blogpost published on the ACTION website which highlights main insights.

Furthermore, based on the different themes that became apparent in the country recommendations, we formulated six overarching recommendations to mainstream citizen science. These were validated in an international citizen science and policy dialogue during the final conference with in total 75 participants. The presentation of the final recommendations is recorded, and both presentation and recording are openly available on Slideshare and ACTION and ECSA Youtube channels, on the ACTION website and on the Eu.citizen-science portal.

The recommendations have been published in an accessible format for the broader citizen science and policy ecosystem and will be available on the ACTION website. Moreover, they are shared with all participants of the masterclasses and are published openly on Zenodo to allow for easy access and correct reference.

Several actions are on-going in the countries where the masterclasses took place as a result of them: in some countries, participants to the masterclass are leading the process of national CS association constitutions, in others there are plans for creating data sharing platforms for improving collaboration among local stakeholders and all of this will possibly lead to further policy impact or positive impacts on the local CS communities. Finally, the masterclasses create new collaborations at local and international level that will last after the end of the ACTION project.

Sustainability plan - impact framework and use	
<i>Openness</i>	The policy recommendations are included both in a deliverable and in a more handy, graphically appealing report. Both are available on the ACTION website and on Zenodo.
<i>Co-design</i>	The recommendations have been co-design with 111 stakeholders across 5 EU countries.
<i>Reflexivity</i>	Each masterclass has been evaluated by participants in order to improve the following ones and for assuring that the reconditions reflect the view of participants.

3 CONCLUSIONS

ACTION delivered several outputs and thanks to its approach to open science and open innovation all of them will remain available to interested audiences for years to come. The main point of reference for this will be the ACTION website (), the ACTION community on Zenodo (<https://www.zenodo.org/communities/actionprojecteu/?page=1&size=20>) and the EU-citizen-science platform (<https://eu-citizen.science/>).

Moreover, the project legacy is visible in the interest of other projects within SwafS and in other domains in its approach and its management of Open Calls and acceleration programme. The “ACTION way” to support researchers and grassroots organisations in doing CS proved to be viable and capable in attracting organisations that would be otherwise excluded from H2020 funds and more ACTION-like projects are emerging.

Finally, what the consortium learned in ACTION, has been integrated in more than 10 proposals (some of which still under evaluation) and in three new projects, one of which, Impetus, can be seen as the continuation and upscaling of ACTION since it will support more than 125 project through open calls, an acceleration program and an European prize for CS.

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